

Energy Policy Monitor

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Conservative Party of Canada
Federal Election Platform 2021
May 2026

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Platform Assessment Details

This document summarizes the results of a standardized energy system assessment of the Conservative Party of Canada's 2021 federal election platform. The assessment compares the platform's stated energy and climate policies against a current-policies baseline to estimate their impact on Canada's greenhouse gas emissions, energy system, and technology deployment pathways.

Policies Repealed	Policies Introduced or Maintained
<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Federal consumer carbon price● Federal clean electricity regulation (CER)● Zero-Emission Vehicle mandate (100% by 2035)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● 30% ZEV mandate for light-duty vehicles by 2030● 15% Renewable Natural gas mandate● 5\$ B in Carbon Capture Tax Credit● Maintain industrial carbon pricing (OBPS)● Replace consumer carbon price with a personal low carbon saving account (50\$/tonne by 2030)● Clean Electricity Regulations

Key Findings

Total Emissions	Sectoral Emissions	Energy Demand (by 2050)
<p>2025: ~ 677 Mt CO²e (vs. 691 Mt baseline with 2021 implemented policies)</p> <p>2030: ~ 633 Mt CO²e (vs. ~ 673 Mt baseline)</p> <p>6% decrease from 2021 baseline</p>	<p>Manufacturing & Industry: Sector most affected by the policies introduced by 2030 (~17.9 Mt CO²e decrease to baseline by 2030)</p> <p>Significant impact on the transportation sector by 2050 (~59.27 Mt CO²e decrease)</p> <p>Electricity: Increase of ~23.03 Mt CO²e by 2050 compared to baseline</p>	<p><i>Electricity Demand:</i> ~300 PJ increase</p> <p><i>Oil products:</i> ~910 PJ decrease</p> <p><i>Total Energy Demand :</i> ~260 PJ decrease</p> <p><i>Natural Gas:</i> ~74 PJ increase</p> <p><i>Hydrogen:</i> ~223 PJ increase</p> <p><i>Bioenergy:</i> ~13 PJ decrease</p>

Emissions Trajectory

Conservative platform modestly reduces emissions below baseline by 2030.

National GHGs

Transport and oil and gas emissions reductions driven by ZEV mandate and CCS investments

Electricity Demand

Capacity Additions

End-use Energy Demand

Some reductions in buildings, driven by RNG mandate (bio-methane and H2 blending)

EPM assessments do not endorse, recommend, or evaluate any policy platform.

This summary does not interpret or evaluate the platform. This assessment applies the same standardized methodology to all parties and platforms.

EPM presents model outputs transparently. Full data, code, and assumptions are publicly available.

About Energy Policy Monitor

The **Energy Policy Monitor delivers** independent, timely analysis of Canada's major energy and climate policy developments. Led by the [Open Insights](#) team, EPM cuts through complexity to provide clear, evidence-based assessments of what new policies mean for emissions trajectories, energy systems, and economic outcomes.

More information about the EPM and other assessments can be found at epm.openinsights.ca.

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